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Analytical Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Determination of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Amlodipine Besylate

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ABSTRACT

A fast, robust RP-HPLC method was developed for simultaneous determination of Bisoprolol fumarate and Amlodipine besylate in tablets. The mobile phase was mixture of Methanol: Acetonitrile: 50mM Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer KH_2PO_4 (25:30:45 v/v) at pH 3.0 at 1 ml/min. The stationary phase was C_{18} Intersil 4.6 x 150 mm (id). UV detection was performed at 267 nm.

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Introduction:

Bisoprolol fumarate is a synthetic β_1 -selective, cardioselective adrenoceptor blocking agent. The chemical name for bisoprolol fumarate is (\pm) -1-[4-[[2-(1-methylethoxy)ethoxy]methyl]phenoxy]-3-[(1-methylethylamino)-2-propanol(*E*)-2-butenedioate (2:1). It is a white crystalline powder, which is readily soluble in water, methanol, ethanol, and chloroform¹. It is official in USP².

Amlodipine besylate, a long-acting calcium channel blocker, is chemically described as 3-ethyl-5-methyl (\pm) -2-[(2-aminoethoxy)methyl]-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-1,4-dihydro-6-methyl-3,5-pyridine dicarboxylate, monobenzenesulphonate.

Amlodipine besylate is a white crystalline powder. It is slightly soluble in water and sparingly soluble in ethanol³. It is official in BP⁴. Beta blocker plus calcium channel blocker combinations have utility in certain cardiovascular diseases like angina pectoris, myocardial infarction and hypertension. A tablet formulation containing bisoprolol fumarate and amlodipine besylate has been recently introduced on the market.

Various methods for determination of bisoprolol by fluorimetry^{5,6}, HPLC⁷⁻⁹ and densitometry¹⁰⁻¹² are reported in literature. Also HPTLC¹³⁻¹⁶, HPLC¹⁷⁻²², spectrophotometry²³⁻²⁸ methods are reported for determination of amlodipine alone or in combination with other drugs. But, literature survey did not reveal any method for simultaneous determination of bisoprolol and amlodipine. The aim of this study was to develop a fast, precise, accurate, rugged and robust HPLC method for simultaneous determination of bisoprolol and amlodipine in tablets. Criteria employed for assessing suitability of proposed method was cost effectiveness and speed of analysis.

Method Development

Equipments used:

A Jasco HPLC was selected for final analysis which was having UV as a detector system. pH meter was made from Lab India (Pico plus), Sonicater from Spectra Lab (BS310), Digital

balance from Mettler toledo, and shimadzu 1700 uv-vis spectrometer was selected for final analysis

Materials:

Methanol and Acetonitrile (HPLC Grade), Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer and O-phosphoric acid (AR Grade) were used during analysis. Amlodipine Besylate and Bisoprolol Fumarate was obtained as a gift sample from Astra Pharmaceuticals, Aurangabad.

Determination of λ max of AML and BISO

The stock standard solutions of BISO and AML were prepared by dissolving 50 mg of each drug in 50 ml of methanol, further dilution was done in selected mobile phase Methanol : Acetonitrile : 50 mM Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer KH_2PO_4 (25:30:45 v/v) and pH was adjusted to 3.0 with 10% O-phosphoric acid. The aliquot portions of stock standard solution were diluted appropriately to obtain a concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of both BISO and AML. The λ_{max} was determined on Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer in the range 200-400 nm using mobile phase as blank. The isoabsorptive point was observed at about 267 nm.

Fig. No. 1

Chromatogram of AML and BISO

Selection of mobile phase

Preparation of standard solutions: BISO standard solution

Accurately weighed quantity 5 mg of BISO was dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to 50 ml mark (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$). The stock standard solution was diluted further with mobile phase to get final concentration of about 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of BISO.

Preparation of standard solutions: AML standard solution

Accurately weighed quantity 5 mg of AML was dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to 50 ml mark (1 µg/ml). The stock standard solution was diluted further with mobile phase to get final concentration of about 20 µg/ml of AML.

Procedure

The mobile phase was allowed to equilibrate with stationary phase until steady baseline was obtained. The standard solution containing mixture of BISO and AML was run and different individual solvents as well as combinations of solvents have been tried to get a good separation and stable peak. Each mobile phase was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42.

Optimized Method

Various mobile phases were tried by trial and error as well as by logical way to find out the exact well suited mobile phase for the estimation of Amlodipine besilate and Bisoprolol fumarate combination.

The optimized mobile phase consisted of Methanol: Acetonitrile: 50mM Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer KH₂PO₄ (25:30:45 v/v) at pH 3.0 was prepared and the pH was adjusted with 10% orthophosphoric acid. It gave sharp and well resolved peaks with symmetry within limits and significant reproducible retention time for BISO and AML .

Figure No.2 Sample ID: blank, Figure No.3 Sample ID: Optimized method (standard) Figure No.4 Sample ID: Optimized method (sample).

Application of proposed method for estimation of AML and BISO Laboratory mixture

Preparation of laboratory mixture (standard)

The standard stock of BISO was prepared by accurately weighed quantity of BISO 5 mg was transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask, shaken vigorously for five minutes and volume was made up to mark. The stock standard solution of AML was prepared in the same manner. The standard solution of AML and BISO were mixed and diluted properly to obtain laboratory mixtures containing a concentration 20µg/ml of BISO and 20µg/ml of AML

Preparation of laboratory mixture (sample)

Five different laboratory mixtures of BISO and AML were prepared by appropriately weighing the quantities of drug samples so as to get the concentration of 20 µg/ml of BISO and 20 µg/ml of AML. The peak area of standard laboratory mixture and sample laboratory mixture was compared to obtained the concentration.

Amount of drug in tablet was calculated using following formula-

$$\% \text{ Estimation} = \frac{A_t}{A_s} \times \frac{D_s}{D_t} \times \frac{W_s}{W_t} \times 100 \text{--- (1)}$$

A_t = Area count for sample solution, A_s = Area count for standard. Solution, D_s =Dilution factor for standard, D_t = Dilution factor for sample, W_s = Weight of standard (mg), W_t = Weight of sample (mg), Results of

estimation of drug in laboratory mixture were shown below.

Table No. 1 Results and statistical data for estimation of AML and BISO in Laboratory mixture.

Sr. no.	Weight of std. (mg)		Weight of sample		Peak area of std		Peak area of sample		% Assay		
	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	
1			5.02	5.01			348150.0	492150.0	99.80	100.01	
2			5.01	5.02			348125.0	492135.5	99.90	99.80	
3	5.01	5.01	4.99	5.03	348160.0	492120.5	348185.5	492160.0	100.41	99.80	
4			5.03	4.99			348135.0	492145.5	99.60	100.41	
5			5.00	5.03			348190.0	492115.0	100.21	99.60	
									Mean	99.98	99.24
									±S.D.	0.32	0.3079
									%R.S.D.	0.32	0.310

Validation of developed RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Amlodipine Besylate and Bisoprolol Fumarate.

1) Linearity and range

According to USP tablet powder equivalent to 80, 90, 100, 110, 120 % of label claim was taken and dissolved in mobile phase, diluted appropriately to

obtain a concentration in the range of 80%-120% of the test concentration. The chromatograms of the resulting solutions were recorded. BISO and AML marketed formulation was found to be linear in the range $\pm 20\%$ of the test concentration of the drugs.

Table No 2 Result and statistical data of Linearity and range study of solution 1 and 5

Injection no	Solution 1 (peak area)		Solution 5 (peak area)	
	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1	278524	393636	417786.0	613656.0
2	278632	393565	417705.0	613755.0
3	278502	393985	419856.5	614076.0
4	278456	393756	417686.0	614089.0
5	279005	393658	418567.0	614178.0
6	277575	393756	417650.0	613786.0
Mean	278449	393726	418208.4	613923.3
±S.D.	472.225	146.647	878.79	216.459
%R.S.D.	0.1695	0.0372	0.210	0.035

Table No 3: Result and statistical data of Linearity and range study of solution 2,3 and 4

Injection no	Solution 2(Peak area)		Solution3(Peak area)		Solution4(Peak area)	
	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1	310614.0	442840.0	349178.0	492140.0	382970.0	541249.0
2	311078.0	442695.0	348165.0	492408.0	383605.0	541845.0
Mean	310846.0	442767.5	348671.5	492274.0	383287.5	541547.0
±S.D.	328.098	102.53	716.30	189.504	449.013	421.436
%R.S.D.	0.1056	0.2316	0.2054	0.0384	0.117	0.0778

Fig. No. 5 Sample ID: Linearity and Range**2) Accuracy**

It was ascertained on the basis of recovery studies performed by standard addition method. The results

Table No. 4: Results and statistical data for Recovery study of AML and BISO

Sr. No.	Weight of standard (mg)		Weight of tablet powder (mg)	Peak area of std		Amount of pure drug added (mg)		Peak area of sample		% Recovery*	
	AML	BISO		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1			149.45			1	1	415017.0	589260.0	99.67	99.74
2	6.90	5.00	149.45	348180.0	492138.0	2	2	479152.0	687995.0	97.73	99.81
3			149.45			3	3	549605.0	785004.0	98.08	99.63
								Mean		98.49	99.73
								±S.D.		1.03	0.091
								%R.S.D.		1.05	0.091

of recovery studies and statistical data were recorded in Table No.5.4 An accurately weighed quantity of reanalyzed tablet powder equivalent to 5 mg of AML (equivalent to 5 mg BISO) was taken in 50 ml volumetric flask; to it standard solution of AML and BISO was added in different proportions. Then volume was adjusted up to the mark with the solvent. Solution was filtered through whatman filter No.42. The aliquot portion of the filtrate was diluted to get final concentration of 20 µg/ml. Accuracy studies were performed by standard addition method as stated in ICH Guideline.

Results were mean of three replicates*3) Precision**

The sample solution was prepared by accurately weighing tablet powder equivalent to 5 mg AML and BISO was dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to 50 ml mark (100 µg/ml). The stock standard solution was diluted further with mobile phase to get final concentration of about 20 µg/ml of AML. Percentage relative standard deviation (% RSD) was found to be < 2 % for within a day and day to day which proved that method was precise.

Table No. 5**Result and statistical data for Interday study**

Sr. no.	Weight of std.(mg)		Weight of tablet powder (mg)	Peak area of std.		Peak area of sample		% Assay *	
	AML	BISO		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1						348150.0	492150.0	98.76	100.03
2	6.85	5.01	149.40	348170.0	492150.0	346055.0	491160.0	98.17	99.83
3						346337.0	492160.0	98.25	99.27
							Mean	98.39	99.7
							±S.D.	0.3200	0.3939
							%R.S.D.	0.3253	0.3950

Results were mean of three replicates*ii) Intraday**

It was performed by using same procedure as under mark interday analysis and absorbance recorded at 3 hrs. interval within a day. The percent label claim was calculated using Equation No. 2 Result and statistical data were shown in Table No. 5.6

4) Ruggedness**i) Different analyst**

The sample solution was prepared by two different analysts and same procedure was followed as

described earlier in precision studies. The assay was calculated by using equation no 2.

.i) Interday (Different days)

Same procedure was performed as under followed in accuracy studies.

Data obtained for day 1, day 2, and day 3 is shown in Table No. 5.

described earlier in precision studies. The assay was calculated by using equation no 2.

5) Robustness

To evaluate the robustness of the developed RP-HPLC method, small deliberate variations in the optimized method parameters were done. The effect of change in flow rate, pH and system change on the retention time and peak area were studied. The method was found to be unaffected by small changes like ± 0.2 change in pH, ± 0.2 change in flow rate and system change.

Table No. 6. Result and statistical data for intraday study

Sr. No.	Weight of Standard (mg)		Weight of tablet (mg)	Peak area of std.		Peak area of sample		% Assay *	
	AML	BISO		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1						346785.0	491501.0	99.22	100.04
2	6.90	5.00	149.20	348178.5	492140.0	347862.0	491425.0	100.64	99.72
3						348050.0	491285.0	99.59	99.99
							Mean	99.93	99.92
							±S.D.	1.004	0.172
							%R.S.D.	0.0100	1.721

*Results were mean of three replicates

Table No. 7 Result and statistical data of Different analyst study.

Sr. no.	Weight of tablet powder (mg)	Peak area of std.		Peak area of sample		% Assay	
		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1	149.45	348175.5	492155.0	346055.0	491150.0	98.85	99.79
2	149.36	348140.0	492185.0	348075.0	492145.0	99.94	99.99
					Mean	99.40	99.89
					±S.D.	0.770	0.1414
					%R.S.D.	0.774	0.1415

Table No. 8. Result and statistical data of flow cahange study

Sr no.		Peak area		Asymetry	
		AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1		348160.0	492120.5	1.760	1.759
2	Flow change by	348278.0	492256.5	1.734	1.775
3	+ 0.2	347012.0	492890.0	1.712	1.747
4		349078.0	492894.0	1.764	1.786
5		348102.0	492168.0	1.757	1.794
	Mean	348126.0	492465.8	1.745	1.772
	±S.D.	736.9084	392.1174	0.022	0.019
	%R.S.D.	0.2116	0.0796	1.260	1.089

Table No. 9
Result and statistical data of flow change study

Sr. no.		Peak area		Asymmetry	
		AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1	Flow change by - 0.2	348440.0	492440.5	1.766	1.760
2		348278.0	492365.5	1.735	1.763
3		347020.0	492298.0	1.719	1.744
4		349400.0	492508.0	1.754	1.776
5		347505.0	492150.0	1.746	1.754
	Mean	348128.6	492352.4	1.744	1.759
	±S.D.	915.645	137.934	0.018	0.012
	%R.S.D.	0.2630	0.0280	1.032	0.670

Table No. 10
Result and statistical data of pH change study

Sr no.		Peak area		Asymmetry	
		AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1	pH change +0.2	349178.0	492140.0	1.759	1.778
2		347256.0	492560.0	1.762	1.762
3		347695.0	492554.0	1.726	1.712
4		348656.0	492659.0	1.788	1.740
5		348233.0	492685.0	1.731	1.755
	Mean	348203.6	492519.6	1.753	1.749
	±S.D.	760.198	220.058	0.025	0.025
	%R.S.D.	0.218	0.0446	0.014	1.428

Table No. 11. Result and statistical data of pH change study

Sr no.		Peak area		Asymmetry	
		AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1		348102.0	492111.0	1.764	1.769
2	pH change -0.2	348958.0	492260.0	1.758	1.752
3		347955.0	492227.0	1.749	1.731
4		348621.0	492564.0	1.775	1.732
5		343481.0	492584.0	1.729	1.746
	Mean	348102.0	492349.2	1.755	1.746
	±S.D.	2240.20	212.66	0.017	0.015
	%R.S.D.	0.643	0.043	0.969	0.899

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analytical method development and validation was performed for RP-HPLC method of estimation of AML and BISO in tablet formulation in accordance with ICH norms for the following parameters:

System suitability, Accuracy, Precision, Ruggedness, Robustness, Specificity, Linearity and range.

The summary of results obtained in analytical method development and validation were mentioned below

Table no.12 Summary of results

Parameters	Acceptance criteria	Results	
		AML	BISO
System suitability	1. % RSD NMT 2%	0.140	1.278
	2. Tailing factor NMT	1.718	1.776
	3. Theoretical plates NLT 2000	2189	3263
Accuracy	%Recovery at each level and % mean recovery 98%-102%	98.49	99.73
Precision	% RSD NMT 2%	1. Interday	0.3253
		2. Intraday	0.0100
Ruggedness (Different analyst)	% RSD NMT 2%	0.774	0.1415
Robustness	% RSD NMT 2%	1.Flow change +0.2	1.260
		2.Flow change -0.2	1.032
		3.pH change +0.2	0.014
		4.pH change -0.2	0.969
Specificity	No interference with placebo	NO INTERFERENCE	
Linearity and Range	Regression coefficient NLT 0.997	0.998	0.999

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